

Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Malonic Acid, Induced by Potassium Permanganate. Part II

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The kinetics of the reduction of mercuric chloride by malonic acid, induced by potassium permanganate, has been studied at different temperatures. The reaction is found to consist of three zones: (i) period of induction, (ii) autocatalysis, (iii) autoinhibition accompanied by a normal reaction. The influence of different inorganic acids, salts, gases, and glass surface has also been studied. A tentative mechanism of the reaction has been suggested, agreeing with the observations made by the authors.

The activation of oxalic acid by oxidising agents was first observed by Dhar¹ and subsequently observed by Oberhauser² and others³⁻⁵. Weiss⁶ suggested a chain mechanism based on the formation of $C_2O_4^{2-}$ radical in the oxidation of oxalic acid by potassium permanganate to explain the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid-permanganate system. Ladbury and Cullis⁷ and Watters⁸ have discussed the postulation of free radicals, such as CO_2^- , and their relevant role in similar mechanism of redox reactions. Prasad and Bhattacharya⁹ studied the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid, induced by potassium permanganate, from the view point of the concentration effect of the inductor on the induction period and extent of reduction of mercuric chloride.

The induced reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid in presence of potassium persulphate was quantitatively studied by Dhar¹ who observed the relationship between the amount of inductor used and the amount of calomel formed. Saxena and Singhal¹⁰ derived a tentative mathematical expression for the velocity of reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic acid in presence of potassium persulphate used as inductor. The present investigations includes the kinetics of the reduction of mercuric chloride by malonic acid, induced by potassium permanganate, and an attempt has been made to suggest the mechanism of this reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

The procedure adopted in studying the kinetics, was the same as described in Part I of this series¹¹. The influence of different gases (N_2, O_2, CO_2), acids (HCl, H_2SO_4 & HNO_3),

1. Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 690; *this Journal*, 1928, **5**, 203.
2. Oberhauser, *Ber.*, 1928, **61**, 521; *Annalen*, 1929, **470**, 111.
3. Wieland and Zilg, *Annalen*, 1937, **530**, 257.
4. Thunberg, *Arch. Physiol.*, 1928, **54**, 6.
5. Able, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1937, **43**, 629.
6. *Trans. Faraday. Soc., Disc.*, 1947, **2**, 188.
7. *Chem. Rev.*, 1958, **58**, 403.
8. *Quat. Report*, 1959.
9. *this Journal*, 1956, **33**, 3.
10. *Ibid.*, 1960, **37**, 405.
11. *This issue*, p. 232.

salts (KCl , K_2SO_4 , KNO_3 , CH_3COONa , and ceric amm. sulphate), and glass surface on the reduction of mercuric chloride was also studied. The rate constants were determined by the well-known formulas for the uni- and bimolecular reactions. The zero-order velocity constant was calculated by the expression:

$$k_0 = dc/dt$$

where dc is the amount of mercurous chloride (in terms of ml of KIO_3) formed during an interval dt .

Influence of Temperature

The reaction was studied at different temperatures. The results obtained at 25° are summarised in Table I and the influence of temperature on the reaction is represented in Fig. 1.

FIG 1

From Table I and Fig. 1, it is observed that at 25° the reaction after a period of induction rapidly develops up to 30 minutes, after which its velocity diminishes. It exhibits zero order for a short period in its later stages. These observations lead to the conclusion that the whole course of the reaction consists of three zones: (i) period of induction, (ii) autocatalysis, (iii) autoinhibition accompanied by a normal reaction for a short period, and may be governed by a chain mechanism.

Fig. 1 also shows that an increase of temperature increases the velocity of the overall reaction and affects its various zones. The period of induction decreases, but the rate of autocatalysis increases and its period is shifted to early intervals. An interesting feature of the reaction is that the reduction of mercuric chloride does not proceed to completion. The maximum reduction is about 55%. The temperature coefficient of the reaction during its normal course is found to be 1.32 between 25° and 35° and the corresponding energy of activation and entropy of activation are found to be 5.1 kcal. and -67.5 e.u. respectively.

TABLE I

$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2=0.1M$. $\text{HgCl}_2=\text{KMnO}_4=0.01M$. Temp. = 25° .
Period of induction = 9 min.

Time.	x .	$a-x$.	k_0 .	k_1 .	k_2 .
0 min.	0	..	..	..	..
10	1.80ml	8.20ml	0.1800	0.01986	0.00219
20	3.20	6.70	0.1400	0.01929	0.00235
30	3.60	6.40	0.0400	0.01488	0.00185
60	4.40	5.60	0.0260	0.00967	0.00130
120	4.80	5.20	0.0066	0.00545	0.00077
180	5.05	4.95	0.0041	0.00385	0.00055
240	5.20	4.80	0.0025	0.00305	0.00045
300	5.35	4.65	0.0025	0.00255	0.00038
360	5.50	4.50	0.0025	0.00221	0.00034

Influence of Concentration of the Reactants

Table II shows that the reduction of mercuric chloride increases, though not proportionally, by increasing the concentration of any of the reactants.

TABLE II

Temp. = 25° .

$\text{HgCl}_2=\text{KMnO}_4=0.01M$.		$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2=0.1M$ $\text{KMnO}_4=0.01M$		$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2=0.1M$ $\text{HgCl}_2=0.01M$	
Malonic acid.	Calomel formed.	HgCl_2 .	Calomel formed.	KMnO_4 .	Calomel formed.
0.05 M	0.077913 g.	0.005 M	0.077913 g.	0.001 M	0.030137 g.
0.10	0.110967	0.010	0.110967	0.002	0.051942
0.15	0.129855	0.020	0.148743	0.004	0.080274
0.20	0.146382	0.030	0.165270	0.008	0.102884
0.25	0.155826	0.040	0.177075	0.016	0.120411
0.30	0.162909	0.050	0.186519	..	..

Influence of Gases

To study the influence of different gases on the reduction of mercuric chloride, the gases were bubbled separately through the reaction mixture at a uniform rate for 1 hr. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

$\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{COOH})_2=0.1M$. $\text{HgCl}_2=\text{KMnO}_4=0.01M$. Temp. = 25° .

Gas.	Calomel formed.
Nil	0.099162 g.
Nitrogen	0.108606
Oxygen	0.118050
Carbon dioxide	0.109786

The data obtained show that the three gases exert an accelerating influence on the velocity of the formation of Hg_2Cl_2 , the effect of oxygen being the greatest. The maximum reduction is also increased by 7% in presence of oxygen.

Influence of Glass Surface

The amount of mercurous chloride formed was also noted during 120 min. by adding different number of glass beads to the reaction mixture with a view to effecting variations in the surface/volume ratio. The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV
Conditions same as in Table III.

No. of beads	..	Nil	125	250	500	1000
Calomel formed (g.)	..	0.110967	0.113328	0.114508	0.110967	0.110967

Table IV shows that the reduction is not affected by glass surface, suggesting that surface/volume ratio plays no role in the reaction.

Influence of Acids

The influence of different acids (Table V) on the reduction of mercuric chloride was studied to ascertain the role of hydrogen ions in the kinetics.

TABLE V
Conditions same as in Table III.

Conc. of the acid.	HCl		HNO_3		H_2SO_4		CH_3COOH	
	P.I.	* KIO_3 .	P.I.	* KIO_3 .	P. I.	KIO_3 .	P.I.	KIO_3 .
..	8' 45"	4.7 ml	8' 45"	4.70ml	8' 45"	4.7 ml	8' 45"	4.77ml
0.01N	6' 40"	2.9	6' 35"	4.35	8' 30"	4.5	8' 45"	4.65
0.02	5' 15"	2.0	5' 10"	4.10	5' 25"	4.3	8' 45"	4.70
0.04	3' 55"	0.8	3' 40"	3.20	3' 50"	3.8	8' 45"	4.70

P.I. denotes period of induction.

* KIO_3 used during 120 min.

Table V shows that most of the acids used retard the reduction of mercuric chloride, the retarding capacities being in the order: $\text{HCl} > \text{HNO}_3 > \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Acetic acid exerts no effect on the reduction of mercuric chloride. These results lead to assume that H^+ ions inhibit the reduction of mercuric chloride.

Influence of Salts

The amount of mercuric chloride reduced was estimated in 120 minutes in presence of different salts in order to ascertain the influence of the salts on the reaction. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE VI

Conc. of salt.	KCl		K ₂ SO ₄		KNO ₃		CH ₃ COONa		Ceric amm. sulphate	
	P.I.	KIO ₃ .	P.I.	KIO ₃ .	P.I.	KIO ₃ .	P.I.	KIO ₃ .	Conc. of salt.	KIO ₃ .
..	8'45"	4.70ml	8'45"	4.70ml	8'45"	4.70ml	8'45"	4.70 ml	..	4.7ml.
0.01N	10'30"	3.35	9'30"	4.85	8'40"	4.75	10'40"	5.20	0.00005M	4.7
0.02	11'0"	2.70	9'50"	5.00	8'45"	4.80	12'50"	5.60	0.00010	4.7
0.03	..	..	..	..	..	..	12'10"	5.80	..	..
0.04	11'25"	1.90	10'40"	5.15	8'45"	5.00	11' 0"	5.60	..	..
0.06	..	..	..	..	..	..	9'15"	4.75	..	..
0.08	..	..	..	..	..	..	7' 5"	3.80	..	..

Table VI shows that ceric ammonium sulphate exerts no influence on the amount of mercuric chloride reduced. Potassium chloride has a negative influence, whereas salts like potassium sulphate and potassium nitrate exert positive influence. It is interesting to note that sodium acetate favours the reduction up to a certain concentration, beyond which it exerts a negative influence. The period of induction is also affected in presence of these salts.

DISCUSSION

Formation of the stable activated complex, its slow decomposition providing free radical and Mn³⁺ ion, and the chain mechanism involving free radical are evident from the negative value of the entropy of activation¹². The reaction develops through various zones and may be governed by a chain mechanism as shown below:

The period of induction is the time required for the formation of the complex $\text{K}_3\text{Mn}(\text{C}_3\text{H}_2\text{O}_4)_3$ and its slow thermal decomposition to produce Mn^{3+} ion which produces $\text{C}\cdot\text{H}(\text{COOH})_2$ to provide finally CO_2^- radical responsible for the reduction of mercuric chloride.

12. Glasston, "Text Book of Physical Chemistry", 1930, pp. 1103-1110.

13. Cartledge and Nichols, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 3057.

The inhibiting influence of inorganic acids, viz., HCl, HNO₃, and H₂SO₄, may be attributed to the less formation of C₂O₄²⁻ radical. The H⁺ ions, furnished by the acids, suppress the formation of C₂O₄²⁻ ions (step 7 b) which produces CO₂⁻ radical (step 8).

Sodium acetate removes H⁺ ions and stabilises C₂O₄²⁻ ions with the result that the chains are elongated and reduction of mercuric chloride is increased; but when the concentration of sodium acetate is in large excess, a fraction of it reacts with H⁺ ions and the rest exerts kinetic salt effect.

Carbon dioxide exerts a catalysing influence on the reduction of mercuric chloride, which is due to the formation of more CO₂⁻ radicals as a result of interaction of CO₂ and an electron in presence of the reducing agents¹⁴.

which brings the reduction of mercuric chloride.

The accelerating effect of oxygen is due to the rapid oxidation of glyoxalic acid (step 7a) to furnish more C₂O₄⁻ ions which ultimately furnish CO₂⁻ radical as an interaction with Mn³⁺ ions (step 8).

FIG. 2

The fall in conductance (Fig. 2) in the initial stages again confirms the formation of the complex. When the complex begins to decompose and precipitation starts, it becomes constant.

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